

DIGITAL LEARNING REVOLUTION: IDENTIFYING THE INFLUENCE OF DEPENDENCY ON ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TOOLS TOWARDS THE KNOWLEDGE ACQUISITION OF STUDENTS

Daniella Louise D.L. Bacallo ¹, Paul Edward G. Bie ¹, Rhiann Yshin C. Tulabut ¹, Alellie Jireh M. Pineda¹, Andrei P. Vicente ¹, Arizelle R. De Vera ¹, Ethan Jmiel F. Sawal ¹, John Louise M. Marcaida ², Ryan C. Dizon ²

¹ Senior High School Department, Our Lady of Fatima University, Philippines

² Department of Physical Education, Our Lady of Fatima University, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13359360>

ABSTRACT

As artificial intelligence tools (AITs) lead the technological revolution, the education sector and other institutions are doing their best to adapt and accommodate this innovation. AITs can be utilized in many ways and have been proven to provide positive changes and benefits to a student's learning. However, the use of AI may also prove to be detrimental to the scholastic development of a student, which may raise concerns regarding academic integrity and ethical use. Thus, this study aimed to deeply understand how the dependency on AITs can influence students' knowledge acquisition. To do this, the study employed a semi-structured interview to gather the perceptions and opinions of 15 Grade 11 and 15 Grade 12 STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) strand students, for a total of 30 participants. After the data gathering procedure, data analysis and interpretation were done using Braun and Clarke's thematic analysis. From the analyzed data, five themes that could describe the influence of AITs on the knowledge acquisition of students in higher educational institutions have emerged, namely: (1) AITs improve a student's scholastic performance; (2) the underlying complexities of AI utilization on students' output; (3) AITs' accessibility and endless possibilities are compelling for usage; (4) the impact of AITs on students; and (5) a vague link between AI utilization and academic dishonesty. The findings of this study may provide a better understanding of the implications of AI utilization in the educational field and the integrity of academia.

Keywords: *Academic dishonesty, Academic integrity, Artificial Intelligence in Education, Generative AI*

INTRODUCTION

The launch of artificial intelligence (AI) technology around the world has brought about astounding yet disruptive technological advancements. This novel technology was defined by Popenici and Kerr (2017) as computing systems capable of exhibiting behaviors and functions that are typically associated with how the human brain operates, such as learning, adapting, integration, self-correction, and data processing for advanced problem-solving. Schwab (2016) portrays AI technology as the synthesis of technologies, one that erases the distinctions in the physical, digital, and biological spheres. Its development has been recorded at an unprecedented exponential rate. Consequently, many aspects are also being reshaped and influenced at a rapid pace, including the education sector. Educational systems, organizations, and institutions in the Philippines, although lagging, have begun to reconceptualize their approaches under "Education 4.0" (Siena et al., 2019). Education 4.0 marks the shift from conventional to a more personalized learning environment, where the integration of AI in education (AIEd) pioneered the structure of Education 4.0 and 5.0 by designing an environment that is responsive and apt for every individual, student, and educator alike (Rane et al., 2023).

The rise of AI technology is prominent and inevitable in this age. Its influence on the world is apparent in many institutions, including the education system, nonetheless. Based on a report, experts expected that AIEd would progress by about 43% in the period 2018–2022 (Educause, 2018). However, it is believed that due to the developments in technology, it will surpass the earlier predictions (Educause, 2019). During the period of COVID-19, there was a significant rise in employing online learning platforms and AI-related tools for education. The Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) released a report in 2023 regarding the state of higher educational institutions. The report revealed an increase in the utilization of online platforms to aid in education. At least half of the higher education student population from 7 countries, which included Thailand, Cambodia, Myanmar, Vietnam, Singapore, Brunei, and Malaysia, can access and utilize these technologies (Lim et al., 2023). In the Philippines, de Villa (2024) reported that three in five educators use AI in research and writing. On the other hand, forty-nine percent (49%) of the educators admitted they use technology to prepare their lesson plans. Meanwhile, it was reported that a survey conducted by Instructure revealed that eighty-three percent (83%) of students use generative AI for research and writing, and another fifty-two percent (52%) use it to aid them in exam preparations (Pascual, 2023; Gajete, 2023).

While the use of artificial intelligence tools (AIT) in education provided substantial guidance and contributed to many benefits for the education sector, their utilization is still up for debate. The use of AI in education raised ethical and privacy concerns over plagiarism, academic dishonesty, and data security (Bin-Nashwan et al., 2023).

Moreover, helping educators effectively integrate AI into their instructional strategies requires pertinent assistance and training (Borbajo et al., 2023). In addition, when proper AI strategies are not used by students in a particular learning situation, learning attitudes are negatively impacted. AI can improve educational opportunities, but excessive dependence is a hindrance to students' capacity for critical thought and problem-solving. Students' capacity for independent and creative thought is diminished if they rely too much on AI-driven solutions (Habib et al., 2023). Moreover, numerous studies have been conducted on students using AITs in their education. AITs can significantly reduce the amount of time spent on a task and are dependable (Baskara, 2023). As observed, some research opposes the use of these, arguing that students risk becoming overly dependent on them in the future, which either impaired their learning or lost their interest in learning (Wogu et al., 2018). On the other hand, Ouyang and Jiao (2021) asserted that students ought to utilize the new technology. Because, if it is used correctly, they can learn new things and broaden their knowledge. However, in the Philippines, there is a lack of research that acknowledges the reliance of students, specifically learners in specialized upper secondary education or senior high school (SHS) students, on AIT in their learning. Moreover, there are hardly any discussions on how SHS students, under different strands and tracks, planned to use AI and how well they could understand the concepts that AI produces. A reason why the Philippines lacks any study about AIEd is due to the eminent disadvantages and apparent exploitation of the technology. Subsequently, many educators judge how AIEd obstructed the process of teaching and learning. However, they failed to notice the potential of AIEd. This study will not only focus on the challenges or drawbacks of the usage of AI but also on the positive effects of the usage of AI in education. With that, this research can fill the gaps left by the other researchers.

Owing to the reliance of students on Artificial Intelligence Tools (AIT), this research aimed to understand the potential drawbacks or limitations associated with the use of AIT on the ability of senior high school (SHS) students to learn in higher education institutions in the Philippines. This study sought to identify the factors influencing students' dependency on AI tools by examining both external and internal determination. By concentrating on known aspects, it is feasible to effectively assess the factors that impact students' decisions to utilize AI tools. Moreover, this study was realistic by recognizing the constraints of resources, time, and information. In doing so, this study ensured that the goals set forth were reachable within the goals provided, taking a practical approach to the research process. Furthermore, the study is designed to address current knowledge gaps in the field by providing timely research that contributes to the ongoing discourse surrounding the integration of AIEd, ensuring that the research remains at the forefront of addressing the opportunities and challenges that SHS students may face in the context of the Digital Learning Revolution. This investigation's insights, which were intended to ascertain the factors leading to the application of Artificial Intelligence Tools (AIT) to a student's learning and the potential drawbacks and opportunities AI offered, proved to be favorable and beneficial to the education sector. This research provided significant information on the matter of AI utilization in academia. Additionally, being the subject of the study, the learners, specifically senior high school (SHS) students, would be more knowledgeable regarding the impacts of the use and overdependence of AI on their scholastic performance. Moreover, educators may also find this useful as they guide

learners to responsible, ethical, and fair use of AI tools. Finally, this study may be of assistance to future researchers who wish to pursue a similar topic.

With the rapid emergence of AIT in the contemporary world, it has demonstrated its convenience in various aspects of life. Contrary to this, Adiguzel et al. (2023) questioned how far AIT can contribute to education, further advising additional analysis and research. Even with its favorable contributions, it is possible to say that AI is not working perfectly up to this day, as said by Akgun and Greenhow (2021). Students who rely too much on AIT have issues with creativity, intellect, and a deep mistrust of their abilities (Habib et al., 2023). Solutions to the problems raised about AI contributed to this study by providing a basis for topics and subjects that needed to be focused on. Relatively, Bin-Nashwan et al. (2023) raised many issues about AIT; among them is plagiarism. Solutions that could help with the problem of plagiarism include using a detection tool capable of detecting plagiarism and AI-generated content, educating students on the ethical implications, and encouraging less use of AI tools. A similar problem with the use of ChatGPT is the generation of false references where it references authors or studies that do not exist (Teel et al., 2023). A solution that could help with this is setting guidelines where the authors present the text copy of the referenced work and teach students the importance of citing correctly. Because of the growing presence of AIT in education, it is important to create an environment that develops a student's cognitive abilities. AITs, which specifically help students with their academic tasks, cannot be eliminated from a student's academic experience, particularly if they have already left a positive impression. It is wiser to employ AI as guidance or implement guidelines for responsible and fair utilization rather than letting these AITs do all the work while leaving nothing for the learner. Knowing the ways to solve or lessen the rising issues of AI is beneficial, especially since reliance on AI could be detrimental to not only oneself but to others as well. It is also essential for teachers to guide students in the right direction when using AI to not harm their cognitive thinking but to improve their mental capabilities.

Unveiling the Fourth Industrial Revolution

Because of humanity's constant efforts to raise their standard of living, civilizations, societies, and even individual lifestyles have all undergone tremendous change. Systems have evolved to be efficient because of the technologies that have been invented and implemented. Just imagine: the First Industrial Revolution (IR 1.0) harnessed nature through water and steam to mechanize labor; towards the Second Industrial Revolution (IR 2.0), electrical power was used for mass production; and as the 21st century neared its dawn, the Third Industrial Revolution (IR 3.0) marked the possibility for automated productions utilizing electronics and information technology (IT). In today's age, the world may be entering a new realm, a new world of possibilities, a new era. The technological advancements made during IR 3.0 paved the way for another revolution: the Fourth Industrial Revolution (IR 4.0). The arrival of IR 4.0 overlaps with IR 3.0 as it also utilizes electronics and IT as its foundation. However, IR 4.0 is more prominent as it introduced the world to the future of cyber-physical systems (CPS). CPS is designed to integrate intricate computing networks and technologies into the real, physical world which is further enforced by human interaction (Ashibani & Mahmoud, 2017; Gunes et al., 2014).

As the nouveau technology continues to bring forth innovations, there will be more opportunities ahead as the integration of these cyber-physical systems is further utilized, altering and influencing the fundamentals this world has been built on. The growth of CPS will be accompanied by Artificial Intelligence (AI) (Chao, 2023).

“A gift of intelligence from intelligence.” This expression was made as people became aware of AI's capacity to mimic human logic and reasoning (Estrellado & Miranda, 2023). AI can be defined as the pinnacle of conception relating to various computer-related technologies that can operate anthropomorphically. The emergence of AI-fueled the beginning of the Fourth Industrial Revolution. Subsequently, this has pushed diverse fields, sectors, management, and governance to acknowledge and respond appropriately to the effects this modern technology presents. It has also brought many changes to the way of life of mankind. This was a testament to how much AI has impacted human activity and society's inner workings. As profitable and advantageous as it may seem, the Fourth Industrial Revolution was accompanied by many challenges. According to Schwab (2016), the Fourth Industrial Revolution is disruptive because of its aggressive progression and development, unlike any other revolution. In the industrial setting, many manufacturers have opted for the use of AI instead of a human workforce. AI in the digital era poses concerns regarding personal data privacy (Van Rijemenam, 2023). The aforementioned problem is also one that is experienced by governments, wherein they would face criticism from citizens should they overtly exercise excessive authority over people by exploiting surveillance systems and digital infrastructure. Even the education sector frets about whether these technologies may replace educators in imparting knowledge to learners. Such are the worries experienced by different sectors. As these problems remained unsolved, dissatisfaction, uneasiness, and unfairness continued to arise within the populace. The emergence of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, which leverages the Third Industrial Revolution, is inevitable. Thus, these various sectors must be able to cope and implement comprehensive responses befitting the situation. Indeed, it is a difficult task to conserve the interests of people without compromising advocacy for innovation and technological progress. However, this is a crucial step that has to be made.

A Glimpse of Education 4.0

Education helps in developing an individual's character, thoughts, interpersonal, and intrapersonal skills and even equips them with skills that will be usable in the real world (Al-Shuaibi, 2014). As such, education must mirror the environment in which it is preparing its learners (Alda et al., 2020). Mankind is now under the influence of electronics and information technology. A digital era, as one may refer to it, Additionally, due to the never-ending breakthrough in technological advancement, it is also currently facing the emergence of artificial intelligence. Therefore, a sector that has a massive impact on society should be immediate in implementing the necessary means to cope with these shifting conditions. However, it seems that the current educational frameworks are not living up to the expectations of this modern generation. Per this concern, the strategy created by the education sector is the introduction of “Education 4.0.” The keynote of this Education 4.0 is its integration with Information and Communication Technologies (ICT). This would help prepare students for navigating the intricacies of the Fourth Industrial

Revolution (Siena et al., 2019). Moreover, Education 4.0 enforced a more adaptive and responsive learning environment for the learners. When compared to Education 3.0, which is a general approach, the proposed model catered to the needs of every student, hence creating an engaging and productive experience in a classroom-based setting (Rane et al., 2023). The implementation of this paradigm is beneficial as it achieves two (2) objectives: to prepare students for the real world and to facilitate a flexible, conducive, and immersive learning atmosphere for students and teachers.

Every single person in this world has the basic right to have an education and to learn. One of the most prominent people in history, Nelson Mandela, believed that education was power, a key to obtaining knowledge and various viewpoints that helped open countless possibilities for many. Mandela (1990) said that “*education is the most powerful weapon which one can use to change the world.*” True to their words, education has the potential to change the world as it shapes individuals to be empowered and fosters creativity where which can be expressed towards the improvement of society. It can transform the world as much as it does influence the minds of a person. However, the world is at a rapid pace of development. Thus, the education sector must transform and remodel its approaches to better fit the contemporary world.

Academic Dishonesty: A Threat to the Academe

As AIT's impression rose across the education sector, there is no doubt that everyone has not heard of what it offers. One of which is academic dishonesty, which pertains to actions by students taking part in illicit activities, such as cheating and plagiarism (Désiron & Petko, 2022). ChatGPT, an interactive chatbot capable of creating cohesive and informative human-like responses upon user input (Lo, 2023), is one of the AITS known to have the capabilities to ease a learner's hassle in writing their academic tasks. Contrary to this, entrusting all the work solely to an AIT, without appropriate cross-checking, encourages the act of plagiarism, subsequently placing a student's academic integrity at risk. Following this, plagiarism is an act of forgery, piracy, and fraud that is considered a severe academic crime that is also against copyright laws (Dhammi & Ul-Haq, 2016).

Users are oblivious to the fact that AI-generated research is prone to falsifying and fabricating works done by other authors, emphasizing imminent challenges, according to data found by Elali & Rachid (2023). Concerning the fabrication of works, AITs, such as ChatGPT, tend to generate fake or fictitious references even with the presence of a formal citation (Teel et al., 2023). Furthermore, with the constant development of AIT, certain software can be utilized for cheating and lead to issues about bias and student learning outcomes since it makes it difficult to discern between genuine writings produced by students and content created by artificial intelligence (Sarker et al., 2023; Cotton et al., 2023). However, it is conceived that AITs have contributed various benefits when it comes to a student's academe and the academe itself, efficiently saving learners' time and effort. A plethora of issues have surfaced, particularly ones connected with academic dishonesty. Hence, it poses an impending threat to the academic evaluation process, which heavily relies upon the authenticity of student submissions, and the objectives of education, which are to promote student originality and creativity (Ifelebuegu et al., 2023; Sarker et al., 2023). These dishonorable acts of dishonesty called into question the

fundamental purpose of education, which was to foster inventiveness and uniqueness, since AITs, cause multiple discrepancies and errors if left neglected and not cross-checked by teachers and students. Furthermore, the accuracy and relevancy of the lessons taught by the teachers to their students hold great significance to the field of education, for it assures that the information they have been taught is reliable, accurate, and credible (Mhlanga, 2023).

Adversities of Excessive Reliance in AIEd

As learners dove into the vast opportunities that AIT may offer in their academe, there is an underlying tendency that one grows dependent on AIT. Its overpowering convenience urged learners to steer into a path of neglect of interpersonal relationships that exist between students and teachers once AIT becomes the primary source of learning. If these interactions are left ignored, the student's holistic development and critical thinking are hindered. Furthermore, the absence of an educator's guidance negatively impacts a student's emotional state (Abbas et al., 2023). Additionally, leaning on AIT too much results in a diminished social development of a student, which contradicts the objectives of education which are human interaction, socialization, and student-to-student collaboration (Ifelebuegu et al., 2023). Furthermore, aside from social concerns, dependency on AIT posed conspicuous issues on cognitive processes. Since not everyone possesses the ability to think as swiftly as a chatbot, this opened the possibility of obstructing a student's creative thinking, where a student may experience cognitive fixation, or the inability to create diverse ideas than what the AIT had to offer. Regarding this, excessive reliance on AIT only fixated students' thoughts rather than allowing them to grow. Moreover, it jeopardized those who are still enhancing their creative confidence and led to a sense of distrust in one's capabilities (Habib et al., 2023).

Despite an AIT's ability to come up with fresh ideas, its credibility remained questionable for it derived its answers from pre-existing data. Eventually, this rose to ethical challenges and concerns about intellectual property and plagiarism, which critically affected a student's ability to think creatively and maintain their academic integrity (Habib et al, 2023). Even though AIT has the potential to offer tremendous opportunities to a student's academia, it is advised to raise knowledge of its limitations. To further emphasize the act of using ChatGPT in a fair, secure, and considerate manner towards students, teachers are encouraged to assist students in developing an informed and critical opinion on the use of AIT, whether within or outside the classroom. Additionally, the act of questioning the output of ChatGPT when inquired should be fostered as well (Mhlanga, 2023). With regards to this, AIT may have been proven to be beneficial to a certain extent to a student, but none can hide the fact that it portrayed several issues concerning its usage, where one of which is over-dependence. All of which solely led to the stunted development of a student cognitively and socially.

Research Questions

This study strove to comprehend the impact of students' dependency on utilizing artificial intelligence tools on their knowledge acquisition. Specifically, this research aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What are the benefits of using Artificial Intelligence tools in students' education?
2. What are the challenges faced by the students who rely on Artificial Intelligence Tools?
3. What are the factors that influenced students' reliance on Artificial Intelligence tools?
4. How do Artificial Intelligence tools implicate the integrity of education?

METHODOLOGY

The study utilized a qualitative research technique. As stated by Creswell (2014), qualitative research is an investigation technique that is grounded in understanding various research that investigates social or human difficulties. The investigator constructed a comprehensive, multifaceted image, examined precise perspectives of the data, and carried out the investigation in a natural environment. Meanwhile, this study utilized a phenomenological approach to determine the drawbacks, opportunities, and factors that influenced the knowledge acquisition of students concerning their reliance on artificial intelligence (AI). Phenomenology is defined as a philosophical tradition, one that takes curiosity in the lived experiences of an individual through an event (Russell & Field-Springer, 2022). Beyond a method of inquiry, it sheds light on the connections and relations of perceptions to phenomena through interpretation. All this is necessary to comprehend the lived world of mankind at a conscious level (Qutoshi, 2018). The chosen participants in this study are the Grade 11 and 12 Senior High School students from the Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) strand. The participants are divided into two groups: mainly, 15 Grade 11 STEM students and 15 Grade 12 STEM students. In total, there were 30 participants selected and interviewed in this study. The participants who are chosen in this study are those who rely on and use AI tools to aid them in their academic outputs. Participants of this study were chosen using purposive sampling. According to Campbell et al. (2020), purposive sampling is the process of better matching the sample to the goals and objectives of the research, strengthening the thoroughness of the research and the accuracy of the data and findings. Purposive sampling is a non-probability sampling method that occurs when elements selected for the sample are chosen through the judgment of the researcher.

In collecting data from the participants, the researchers utilized an interview specifically a semi-structured interview. An interview, as defined by Brinkmann (2014), means to obtain experiences and perspectives from an individual as a means to make sense of a certain phenomenon. To be more specific, a self-made, semi-structured type of interview was the main instrument used to obtain information from the participants. According to Adams (2015), a semi-structured interview uses a combination of close- and open-ended questions to gather information from the interviewee or the participants. It consists of a

comprehensive interview guide that is used when personalized and subjective knowledge is lacking regarding a phenomenon (McIntosh & Morse, 2015). To further identify the influence of AIT dependency on the knowledge acquisition of SHS STEM students, this research primarily concentrated on utilizing the Thematic Analysis method by Braun & Clarke (2006). Thematic analysis is known for examining, finding, and summarizing patterns found within data. It thoroughly defines and minimally arranges the data set. Correspondingly, research ethics was practiced throughout the study process.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Theme 1: AITs improve a student's scholastic performance

Since the release of artificial intelligence (AI) tools in the world, it has influenced students' performance at school. Wherein the use of AITs has benefitted the students from a variety of advantages. These advantages included helping students with their tasks or assignments and encouraging them to complete their work with less difficulty. AI is another kind of thing that not only evaluates performance but also takes proactive measures to make something better (Dhara et al., 2022). Additionally, AI-assisted students' written output, such as essays, research, reflections, etc. Because of its immediate response, it corrects the use of grammar and even gives guidance to the language use of the student. Hence, it benefits students in their academic tasks, performance, and overall education. A case study involving AI stated that the academic study of artificial intelligence can transform many different fields into academic research (Alshater, 2022). Possessing the capacity to evaluate and comprehend vast volumes of material, create scenarios and simulations, and then clearly and concisely convey findings. In this way, artificial intelligence (AI) has greatly improved the efficiency of research.

Subtheme 1.1 The impact of utilization and convenience of GenAI on a student's output.

This subtheme realized that the use of AITs helps the students generate ideas for doing their tasks. As stated by Mhlanga (2023), AI tools can produce logical and contextually appropriate sentences, which helps improve a student's critical and creative thinking. With that justification, the use of AI tools could help students generate ideas and finish their tasks faster. Using AITs made students' tasks easier to do. Research by Chan and Hu (2023) showed the benefits of using GenAI. They found out that it provided convenience, support, and assistance, as well as research and analysis support, to students. Hence, the utilization of AI tools helped students work and achieve their academic tasks more easily.

Subtheme 1.2 AITs as a grammatical assistance provider.

This subtheme focused on one of the benefits that arose from using AITs in education. As stated by O'Neill & Russell (2019), AITs provide students with grammatical assistance due to the automated feedback programs that these applications have. Thus, AI tools like Grammarly, ProWritingAid, and Writing Mentor are becoming well-liked in academic, professional, and social contexts. These applications that provide feedback to users make writing easier and invaluable to many writers and students as they are assisted and receive text generation and sentence completion recommendations that are human-like (Alharbi, 2023).

Theme 2: Underlying complexities of AI utilization on student output

With the rise of technology, AITs have been utilized in education, where they have seen steady development (Pinkwart, 2016). AIEd has brought multiple changes and opportunities for students' learning and development in the overall educational field (Baker et al., 2019). Although this technology came with benefits, it also presented challenges that students may inevitably experience as it becomes more intertwined in their academic journey. Generative AI models like Chat Generative Pre-Trained Transformer (ChatGPT) use a large set of data to generate responses to the users' prompts (Gilson et al., 2023). Because of this, there are common challenges students experience with the responses it gives due to it following a set of patterns or codes. The problems arising among participants are, first, the ambiguous or incorrect responses it generates. Secondly, the recognizable text pattern of responses AITs provide is due to it following the same dataset.

Subtheme 2.1 Inaccurate and incomprehensible results.

This subtheme, which emerged as a problem for students when using artificial intelligence tools, is characterized by the complexities associated with the utilization of AI for students' learning outcomes. These underlying complexities served as a detrimental factor in the acquisition of knowledge by students. In this current era, the use of AI presents challenges to students' learning outputs by helping with research, assignments, and ideas, which may contain unreliable and false information that impacts students' work (Rasul et al., 2023). Moreover, learners are inclined to present non-factual information, perpetuating misconceptions that could mislead students. Further, research into the validity of AI-generated questions for higher education has revealed that, although most students considered AI-generated questions to be relevant, clear, and accurate, there were still concerns regarding the dependability of the AI-generated content (Tweissi et al., 2022). These findings implied that AI can be advantageous in educational settings; however, there are still areas where its accuracy may need improvement, especially in tasks involving student interactions and assessments. While AI can forecast student outcomes and deliver feedback, the absence of explainability and transparency in these models can lead to issues such as trust concerns, difficulty comprehending the system, and anxiety among educators (Hall et al., 2023).

Subtheme 2.2 Data Pattern

This subtheme emerged as one of the common problems students mentioned: the obvious and similar text pattern in the AITs' output. Though the problem seems simple, it raised concerns regarding the reliability and creativity of AI-generated texts to produce responses that have no similarity with other responses it has given. A problem that emerged due to the obvious text pattern is the similarity in answers between students who gave similar prompts. A study conducted by Kim et al. (2024) investigated user dissatisfaction when using ChatGPT, where one of the common problems is 'prompt reusing' and the answers being too generic—a problem not far off from the issues mentioned by participants in this study. Having a generic answer to an input can lead to others receiving similar generic responses from the AIT. Moreover, a study by Borji (2023) stated that AITs like ChatGPT rarely encounter a question it hasn't had before due to exposure to various coding examples, leading to the generation of general responses and a lack of originality. Correspondingly AI-generated texts fall short of human-generated texts by lacking the originality and creativity humans have, instead producing texts that are repetitive and formulaic (Mindner et al., 2023).

Theme 3: AITs accessibility and endless possibilities are compelling for usage

With the adaptive innovations made in AI, it has shown significant impacts on different aspects of the contemporary world. One of which is education, which has had major implications, especially for its students (Chen et al., 2020). Consequently, students who use AITs for their academics have found numerous outcomes that portray positive and negative approaches to learning (Zhai et al., 2021). However, finding the effects that AITs have brought is regarded as significant, as is figuring out the rationales behind a student's usage of AIT. The usefulness of AITs in the education sector, particularly ChatGPT, has a substantial impact on the reasons why students use AIT (Abdaljaleel et al., 2024). Owing to this, students utilize AITs as an academic companion with their capability to produce responses in a short time, and due to their convenience, students employ AITs because they tend towards laziness.

Subtheme 3.1 AITs as an academic companion.

Due to the features provided by AITs, they have given students numerous benefits—and oftentimes challenges—when it comes to their education. Hence, this subtheme has recognized AITs as an "academic companion" according to the supplementary actions it has presented toward the academic career of a student. With its ability to generate instantaneous responses to user inputs and queries, specifically ChatGPT, Gill et al. (2023) noted that it uses AI and Natural Language Processing (NLP) to answer and create realistic answers that are relevant, well-organized, and educational. Thus, students can obtain noteworthy ideas by doing so. In the words of Fitria (2021), AI is said to be a "virtual mentor" due to its ability to adapt information independently to align with the demands and issues encountered by students by recognizing misunderstandings, providing comments and recommendations, and potentially providing answers. Subsequently, this enabled the learners to complete tasks more efficiently, as emphasized by participants in

this study. Additionally, students, especially those with time constraints, use AITs to alleviate the stress of their heavy academic workload. At a certain point, a learner may feel as if they do not have enough time to complete a task. As such, they may look for methods to complete the task at hand before its impending deadline, and consulting an AIT for prompt responses is one such way (Abbas et al., 2024).

Subtheme 3.2 Convenience of AITs as an influence on the inclination of laziness.

The emergence of AITs in education has indeed been relatively recent and has accumulated substantial attention from many educational stakeholders (Cain, 2023), yet their impact has been profound and far-reaching in this facet, most specifically for its students, sparking an influence related to tolerating laziness. Henceforth, this subtheme has surfaced due to AITs being manipulated by students to their benefit because of their inclination to laziness. Findings garnered by Hadi Mogavi et al. (2023) have shown that using AITs, ChatGPT in particular, can only intensify procrastination. Since an AIT can produce timely responses, it is highly probable to instill a sense of control and a belief that the academic task at hand can be accomplished at any time among students, which will only foster the learner to put off the task until the very last minute possible (Abbas et al., 2024). Such acts, where AITs assist in accomplishing academic tasks with the student exerting minimal effort, will simply serve to reinforce habitual tendencies towards sloth.

Theme 4: Impact of AITs to Students

Depending on the type of task assigned to a student, appropriate Artificial Intelligence Tools will be utilized to efficiently help them in their tasks. And based on how they utilize these tools, the results would vary for each of them. Some have seen an improvement in how they did their academic tasks (Chen et al., 2020), while some were left baffled by the results it offered as they deemed it irrelevant or it was too complex for comprehension (Rasul et al., 2023). It is established that AITs can aid, as well as present challenges to a student's outputs. The same can be said about how AITs are affecting how students are learning. The effect of AITs on the knowledge acquisition of students is divided into two: a positive and a negative effect (Farrokhnia et al., 2024).

Subtheme 4.1 Positive Impacts.

The integration of AI Tools in Education is setting a seamless blend with human intellect, perception, and culture. Thus, Artificial Intelligence Tools have revolutionized and innovated much of the educational landscape and will continue to do so in the following years. Analyzing the roles and possible applications of AITs in education from past reports, revealed a role wherein it served as an intelligent tutor, inclined to support the learning of a student by employing a subjective learning system (Hwang, 2020). A commonly used AI technology that has the capability of acting like a tutor is Chatbots (Adiguzel, 2023). Amongst the many Chatbots available on the internet, at least half of the participants responded that they use ChatGPT to aid them in their studies. ChatGPT is capable of a variety of tasks like responding to questions, idea generation, and complex subjects, concepts, or themes explanation. With the use of these AI technology,

participants expressed that they were able to use these AI technologies to help them comprehend a topic, as well as to gain or increase their knowledge regarding a subject matter. Another positive impact of an AIT on students is due to its time-saving feature (Bin-Nashwan et al., 2023). Time is of the essence, especially for a student. Learners must juggle different tasks and outputs, and with limited time they may not be able to accomplish all of these. However, incorporating AITs in their studies would prove to be helpful as they can provide real-time support to students, helping them to manage both their time and tasks. These systems have shown a significant outcome in terms of psychological effect and task efficiency (Li & Jan 2023). Additionally, as the database size and accuracy of a Chatbot increases, the more likely it is to perform better and provide better assistance to students (Adiguzel et al., 2023). AI Tools are continuously being developed to the length of time to aid the people who rely on their services.

Subtheme 4.2 Negative Impacts.

Embracing the use of AITs in higher educational institutions seems commendable as a step for the education sector to adapt and accommodate the rising technological advancements that are influencing it, while also considering the positive impacts it provides to students. However, it is also undeniable that these tools hurt students. When participants were asked about the impacts of AITs on their studies or how they learn, some answered that they are becoming lazy and dependent on AI; some also answered that AI affects their critical thinking. According to Sabharwal et al. (2023), the utilization of AI causes students to become lazy. When a student continuously relies on the assistance of these tools, there is a possibility that they may become passive learners, uninterested in participating in learning processes and learning activities. In their study, they discussed the relationship between artificial intelligence and human laziness, where it was demonstrated that an increase in AI leads to an increase in laziness. Furthermore, this over-dependence on AITs may ultimately lead to decreased critical thinking and decision-making among students. This can be further supported by the findings of Sevnarayan & Potter (2024), explaining that focusing only on the efficiency and ingenuity of such tools would only result in the neglect of technical skills, critical thinking, and creativity.

Theme 5 A vague link between AI Utilization and academic Dishonesty

With the increasing integration and implementation of artificial intelligence tools (AIT) in the academic scene, it has raised concerns in the community. Specifically, employing AITs brought forth ethical issues about how students may use these tools to commit dishonesty (Qadir, 2023). Academic dishonesty is still a prevalent topic in the community. It encompasses all actions a person may take to gain an academic advantage, albeit unfairly (Benson et al., 2019). Pavela's (1997) conceptual framework defined what acts are diametrical in achieving educational goals, namely: (1) cheating, (2) facilitation, (3) fabrication, and (4) plagiarism. It is debatable whether the use of AITs encourages students to commit the aforementioned actions that implicate academic integrity. The availability of AI-powered and AI-assisted platforms that can be used in education, like paraphrasing software and essay mills, has urged students to commit plagiarism as well

as generate supposedly authentic content (Manley, 2021). According to Abd-Elaal et al. (2019), the utilization of AITs such as text-generators is a tool that violates academic and research integrity, leading to serious misconduct as these tools only encourage dishonest work from the authors. However, Yeralan and Lee (2023) both argue that because of the capabilities of generative AI (GenAI), it can supplement ideas, further improving the brainstorming phase and enhancing the overall thinking process. It is also able to suggest alternative proposals and create numerous drafts, which can help with the structure of the final output. Therefore, it is subjective; it depends on the circumstances and the individuals themselves whether the result of using such tools would be "good" or "bad." Perkins (2023) also reiterates that it would not be necessarily viewed as plagiarism if the student offered accountability and transparency with every output. This varying view of the connection between AI usage and academic dishonesty might be because there have been neither guidelines, policies, nor frameworks proposed or devised to address the ethical concerns that are currently being raised by the integration of AITs in education (Holmes et al., 2018). Until some frameworks or guidelines can be followed or consulted to ascertain whether the use of AITs in the scholastic scene falls under academic dishonesty, the link between these two will remain ambiguous for those in the academic community.

Conclusions

Based on the accumulated findings, the researchers concluded the following:

-
1. Artificial intelligence tools have greatly benefited students with their academic tasks by providing convenient, instant, and logical answers and ideas. They have also provided help with students' written works by aiding with their grammar and sentence structures.
 2. Due to AITs following a set of data or codes, they often pose challenges to students by generating general, wrong, or misleading answers to a student's queries. The problem of general answers leads to students having similar answers to others.
 3. Providing ideas and answers to students instantaneously, helping them with their tasks, and helping them learn from their mistakes are some of the reasons why

students use AITs. Another reason is the convenience of obtaining answers without effort, oftentimes fueled by the student's laziness.

4. The utilization of AITs doesn't inherently damage academic integrity; it depends solely on the students on how they utilize AITs. While some use it honestly and for simple tasks, others use it in a way that can lead to plagiarism.

Recommendations

The purpose of the following recommendations is to provide observations of the following entities concerning how they implement the use of AITs to appropriately fit their needs. Thus, the following recommendations are hereby presented:

1. Students must exercise caution when relying on AI tools for critical thinking tasks, as over-reliance on these tools may hinder the development of essential skills such as analytical thinking, creativity, and independent problem-solving.
2. Students need to avoid blindly accepting AI-generated outputs without verifying their accuracy and relevance.
3. Students need to strike a balance between leveraging AI tools as helpful aids and cultivating one's cognitive abilities, which is key to achieving academic success.
4. Since the influence of AI tools has been proven, teachers need to equip themselves with digital competencies that align with educational goals and transform teaching methods in school learning environments to support students influenced by AI.
5. To improve students' learning outcomes, it is suggested that teachers assess students' needs and allocate time efficiently when students are impacted by AI, concentrating on immediate behavioral cues and delivering prompt support for optimal results.
6. Curriculum developers should make adjustments to the curriculum in response to the rising use of AITs by students.
7. Curriculum developers should integrate AI literacy by developing modules that (1) introduce AITs and how to use them the right way, (2) highlight the wrong way of

using AI and its possible consequences, and (3) discuss the ethical implications of using AITs and how to use them ethically.

8. Curriculum developers should focus on data literacy in the curriculum, ensuring that the students know how to analyze and interpret the outputs from the AITs.
9. Curriculum developers should promote critical thinking skills, problem-solving skills, and creativity, ensuring that despite the rise of AIEd, students will still possess the necessary skills.
10. Educational institutions should emphasize and promote the ethical use of AITs by developing a curriculum that discusses topics like discrimination and bias in AI, privacy, and transparency.
11. Educational Institutions should create programs that combine AI with other fields like healthcare, engineering, and humanities to provide opportunities and prepare students.
12. Educational Institutions should monitor and regularly assess the impacts of AI on students' learning, engagement, and performance to ensure a safe and healthy environment where students can safely use AITs.
13. A similar study must be conducted to determine whether the same findings are established. To ensure the accuracy and reliability of the results, a comparable research project should be conducted to confirm the validity of the findings.
14. Future researchers in the field of AI must consider potential obstacles, including bias and discrimination. Addressing these issues can be achieved by incorporating diversity and inclusivity concepts to ensure that AI is designed with fairness, trust, and transparency in mind.
15. Furthermore, studying the impact of AI on various aspects of education, such as teaching methods, curriculum design, and student engagement, can offer valuable insights for informing future research. Understanding the different interactions between AI and education, as well as the evolution of AI's role in education over the years, can provide valuable insights for future research.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research strictly adheres to the ethical standards set by the institution and the body of knowledge. All information and data coming from the respondents are solely for academic purposes only. In line also with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, the researchers strictly preserved the anonymity and confidentiality of the respondents.

Acknowledgments

The researchers would like to express their heartfelt gratitude and appreciation to the following people who helped them throughout their study, as they would not have finished it without their unending support and efforts. First and foremost, the researchers would like to express their gratitude to God, our Creator, for his unwavering blessing and guidance throughout the process of conducting this study. To John Louise M. Marcaida, LPT, MPES (c), our professor in Practical Research 1. The researchers would like to

thank him for providing constant assistance and patience to the researchers throughout the entire process of composing this paper, which they are grateful for.

To the participants, who provided us with their time and answers during the gathering of our data. The researchers would like to give their acknowledgments to each of the 30 participants from STEM Grades 11 and 12, as they have aided us with their responses, which were substantial in the findings and discussion section of our study. To our teachers and professors, the researchers are eternally grateful for the guidance they provided towards the completion of the paper. And we also acknowledge the wisdom they've given us, which has helped our research improve. Lastly, to our family and friends who supported us in crucial times and who have always been the researchers' sources of support and motivation for this research. The researchers would like to express their warm appreciation for their constant love and support, which gave them the motivation to pursue this study and to see through it until the end.

REFERENCES

- Abbas, M., Jam, F. A., & Khan, T. I. (2024). Is it harmful or helpful? Examining the causes and consequences of generative AI usage among university students. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 21(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-024-00444-7>.
- Abbas, N., Ali, I., Manzoor, R., Hussain, T., & Hussaini, M. H. A. (2023). Role of Artificial Intelligence Tools in Enhancing Students' Educational Performance at Higher Levels. *Journal of Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning and Neural Network (JAIMLNN)* ISSN: 2799-1172, 3(05), 36–49. <https://doi.org/10.55529/jaimlnn.35.36.49>
- Abdaljaleel, M., Barakat, M., Alsanafi, M., Salim, N. A., Abazid, H., Malaeb, D., Mohammed, A. H., Hassan, B. A. R., Wayyes, A. M., Farhan, S. S., Khatib, S. E., Rahal, M., Sahban, A., Abdelaziz, D. H., Mansour, N. O., AlZayer, R., Khalil, R., Fekih-Romdhane, F., Hallit, R., & Hallit, S. (2024). A multinational study on the factors influencing university students' attitudes and usage of ChatGPT. *Scientific Reports*, 14(1), 1983. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-52549-8>
- Abd-Elaal, E.-S., Gamage, S. H. P. W., & Mills, J. E. (2019). Artificial Intelligence Is a Tool for Cheating Academic Integrity. In 30th Annual Conference for the

- Australasian Association for Engineering Education (AAEE 2019): Educators Becoming Agents of Change: Innovate, Integrate, Motivate, 397–403.
- Adams, W. C. (2015). Conducting Semi-Structured Interviews. *Handbook of Practical Program Evaluation*, 1(4), 492–505. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119171386.ch19>
- Adiguzel, T., Kaya, M. H., & Cansu, F. K. (2023). Revolutionizing education with AI: Exploring the transformative potential of ChatGPT. *Contemporary Educational Technology*, 15(3), ep429. <https://doi.org/10.30935/cedtech/13152>
- Akgun, S., & Greenhow, C. (2021). Artificial intelligence in education: Addressing ethical challenges in K-12 settings. *AI and Ethics*, 2(3). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43681-021-00096-7>
- Alda, R., Boholano, H., & Dayagbil, F. (2020). Teacher Education Institutions in the Philippines towards Education 4.0. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 19(8). <https://doi.org/10.26803/ijlter.19.8.8>
- Alharbi, W. (2023). AI in the Foreign Language Classroom: A Pedagogical Overview of Automated Writing Assistance Tools. *Education Research International*, 2023, e4253331. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2023/4253331>
- Alshater, M. (2022). Exploring the Role of Artificial Intelligence in Enhancing Academic Performance: A Case Study of ChatGPT. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4312358>
- Al-Shuaibi, A. (2014). The importance of education. ResearchGate. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/260075970_The_Importance_of_Education
- Ashibani, Y., & Mahmoud, Q. H. (2017). Cyber physical systems security: Analysis, challenges, and solutions. *Computers & Security*, 68, 81–97. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cose.2017.04.005>
- Baker, T., Smith, L., & Anissa, N. (2019, February 25). Educ-AI-tion rebooted? Exploring the future of artificial intelligence in schools and colleges. Nesta. <https://www.nesta.org.uk/report/education-rebooted/>
- Baskara, FX. R. (2023). Chatbots and Flipped Learning: Enhancing Student Engagement and Learning Outcomes through Personalised Support and Collaboration. *IJORER: International Journal of Recent Educational Research*, 4(2), 223–238. <https://doi.org/10.46245/ijorer.v4i2.331>
- Benson, L., Rodier, K., Enström, R., & Bocatto, E. (2019). Developing a university-wide academic integrity E-learning tutorial: a Canadian case. *International Journal for Educational Integrity*, 15(1). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40979-019-0045-1>
- Bin-Nashwan, S. A., Sadallah, M., & Bouteraa, M. (2023). Use of ChatGPT in academia: Academic integrity hangs in the balance. *Technology in Society*, 75(75), 102370. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2023.102370>
- Borbajo, M. N. M., Malbas, M. H., & Dacanay, L. R. (2023). Reforming Education: The Global Impact of Integrating Artificial Intelligence in the Classroom Environment. *American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education* (2993-2769), 1(5), 16–27. <https://grnjournal.us/index.php/STEM/article/view/356/295>
- Borji, A. (2023). A Categorical Archive of ChatGPT Failures. ArXiv (Cornell University). <https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.2302.03494>

- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using Thematic Analysis in Psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77–101.
<https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>
- Brinkmann, S. (2020). *The Oxford Handbook of Qualitative Research* (P. Leavy, Ed.; 2nd ed., pp. 424–456). Oxford University Press. (Original work published 2014)
- Cain, W. (2023). AI Emergence in Education: Exploring Formative Tensions Across Scholarly and Popular Discourse. *Journal of Interactive Learning Research*, 34(2), 239–273.
- Campbell, S., Greenwood, M., Prior, S., Shearer, T., Walkem, K., Young, S., Bywaters, D., & Walker, K. (2020). Purposive Sampling: Complex or Simple? Research Case Examples. *Journal of Research in Nursing*, 25(8), 652–661. NCBI.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1744987120927206>
- Chan, C., & Hu, W. (2023). Students' voices on generative AI: perceptions, benefits, and challenges in higher education. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 20(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-023-00411-8>
- Chao, W. (2023, October 16). The Fourth Revolution: big data & artificial intelligence | The UNESCO Courier. [courier.unesco.org](https://courier.unesco.org/en/articles/fourth-revolution).
<https://courier.unesco.org/en/articles/fourth-revolution>
- Chen, L., Chen, P., & Lin, Z. (2020). Artificial Intelligence in Education: a Review. *IEEE Access*, 8(2169-3536), 75264–75278.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2988510>
- Cotton, D. R. E., Cotton, P. A., & Shipway, J. R. (2023). Chatting and cheating: Ensuring academic integrity in the era of ChatGPT. *Innovations in Education and*

- Teaching International, 61(2), 228–239.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/14703297.2023.2190148>
- Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approach* (4th ed.). Sage Publications Ltd.
- De Villa, K. (2024, January 27). The survey shows how PH vocational schools view AI. INQUIRER.net. <https://newsinfo.inquirer.net/1894979/survey-shows-how-ph-vocational-schools-view-ai>
- Désiron, J. C., & Petko, D. (2022). Academic dishonesty when doing homework: How digital technologies are put to bad use in secondary schools. *Education and Information Technologies*, 28. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-022-11225-y>
- Dhammi, I. K., & UI Haq, R. (2016). What is plagiarism and how to avoid it? *Indian Journal of Orthopaedics*, 50(6), 581–583. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0019-5413.193485>
- Dhara, S., Chatterjee, S., Chaudhuri, R., Goswami, A., & Soumya Kanti Ghosh. (2022). Artificial Intelligence in Assessment of Students' Performance. 153–167. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003184157-8>
- EDUCAUSE, Alexander, B., Ashford-Rowe, K., Barajas-Murphy, N., Dobbin, G., Knot, J., Pomerantz, J., Seilhamer, R., & Weber, N. (2019). *Horizon Report: 2019 Higher Education Edition*. EDUCAUSE. <https://library.educause.edu/~media/files/library/2019/4/2019horizonreport.pdf>
- EDUCAUSE, Becker, S. A., Brown, M., Dahlstrom, E., Davies, A., DePaul, K., Diaz, V., & Pomerantz, J. (2018). *Horizon Report 2018 Higher Education Edition*. EDUCAUSE. <https://library.educause.edu/~media/files/library/2018/8/2018horizonreport.pdf>
- Elali, F. R., & Rachid, L. N. (2023). AI-generated research paper fabrication and plagiarism in the scientific community. *Patterns*, 4(3), 100706. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patter.2023.100706>
- Estrellado, C. J. P., & Miranda, J. C. (2023). Artificial Intelligence in the Philippine Educational Context: Circumspection and Future Inquiries. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 13(5), 16–22. <https://doi.org/10.29322/IJSRP.13.04.2023.p13704>
-
- Farrokhnia, M., Banihashem, S. K., Noroozi, O., & Wals, A. (2023). A SWOT analysis of ChatGPT: Implications for educational practice and research.

- Fitria, T. N. (2021). Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Education: Using AI Tools for Teaching and Learning Process. *Proceeding Seminar Nasional & Call for Papers*, 2654-6590, 134–147.
- Gajete, S. (2023, November 17). Philippine schools now integrate AI into learning: Premiere state U- University of the Philippines at the forefront in Asia. *Global South World*.
<https://globalsouthworld.com/article/philippine-schools-now-integrate-ai-into-learning-premiere-state-u-university-of-the-philippines-at-the-forefront-in-asia>
- Gill, P., & Phythian, M. (2018). *Intelligence in An Insecure World*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Gill, S. S., Xu, M., Patros, P., Wu, H., Kaur, R., Kaur, K., Fuller, S., Singh, M., Arora, P., Parlikad, A. K., Stankovski, V., Abraham, A., Ghosh, S. K., Lutfiyya, H., Kanhere, S. S., Bahsoon, R., Rana, O., Dustdar, S., Sakellariou, R., & Uhlig, S. (2023). Transformative effects of Emerging Era of AI Chatbots, 4(4). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iotcps.2023.06.002>.
-
- Gilson, A., Safranek, C. W., Huang, T., Socrates, V., Chi, L., Taylor, R. A., & Chartash, D. (2023). How Does ChatGPT Perform on the United States Medical Licensing Examination? The Implications of Large Language Models for Medical Education and Knowledge Assessment. *JMIR Medical Education*, 9(9), e45312.
<https://doi.org/10.2196/45312>
-
- Gunes, V., Peter, S., Givargis, T., & Vahid, F. (2014). A Survey on Concepts, Applications, and Challenges in Cyber-Physical Systems. *KSII Transactions on Internet and Information Systems*, 8(12), 134–159.
<https://doi.org/10.3837/tiis.2014.12.001>
- Habib, S., Vogel, T., Thorne, E., & Xiao, A. (2023). How Does Generative Artificial Intelligence Impact Student Creativity? *Journal of Creativity*, 34(1), 100072.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yjoc.2023.100072>
- Hadi Mogavi, R., Deng, C., Juho Kim, J., Zhou, P., D. Kwon, Y., Hosny Saleh Metwally, A., Tlili, A., Bassanelli, S., Bucchiarone, A., Gujar, S., Nacke, L. E., & Hui, P.

(2023). ChatGPT in education: A blessing or a curse? A qualitative study exploring early adopters' utilization

and perceptions. *Computers in Human Behavior: Artificial Humans*, 2(1), 100027. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chbah.2023.100027>

- Hall, E. C., Seyam, M., & Dunlap, D. (2023). Identifying Usability Challenges in AI-Based Essay Grading Tools. *Communications in Computer and Information Science*, 675–680. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-36336-8_104
- Holmes, W., Porayska-Pomsta, K., Holstein, K., Sutherland, E., Baker, T., Shum, S. B., Santos, O. C., Rodrigo, M. T., Cukurova, M., Bittencourt, I. I., & Koedinger, K. R. (2021). Ethics of AI in
- Hwang, G.-J., Xie, H., Wah, B. W., & Gašević, D. (2020). Vision, challenges, roles and research issues of Artificial Intelligence in Education. *Computers and Education: Artificial Intelligence*, 1(1), 100001. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.caeai.2020.100001>
- Ifelebuegu, A. O., Kulume, P., & Cherukut, P. (2023). Chatbots and AI in Education (AIEd) tools: The good, the bad, and the ugly. *Journal of Applied Learning and Teaching*, 6(2). <https://doi.org/10.37074/jalt.2023.6.2.29>
- Kim, Y., Lee, J., Kim, S., Park, J., & Kim, J. (2024). Understanding Users' Dissatisfaction with ChatGPT Responses: Types, Resolving Tactics, and the Effect of Knowledge Level. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3640543.3645148>
- Li, E. Y., & Jan, A. (2023). Impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Enhancing Productivity and Reducing Stress Among Students. *The 23rd International Conference on Electronic Business*, 23, 334–342. https://iceb.johogo.com/proceedings/2023/ICEB2023_paper_9.pdf
- Lim, M. A., Anabo, I. F., Phan, A. N. Q., Elepaño, M. A., & Kuntamarat, G. (2023). The State of Higher Education in Southeast Asia. <https://asean.org/wp->

content/uploads/2023/08/The-State-of-Higher-Education-in-Southeast-Asia_11.2022.pdf

- Lo, C. K. (2023). What Is the Impact of ChatGPT on Education? A Rapid Review of the Literature. *Education Sciences*, 13(4), 410. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci13040410>
- Mandela, N. (1990, June 24). Nelson Mandela visited Madison Park HS In Roxbury in 1990. GBH News. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=b66c6OkMZGw>
- Manley, S. (2021). The use of text-matching software's similarity scores. *Accountability in Research*, 30(4), 1–27. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08989621.2021.1986018>
- McIntosh, M. J., & Morse, J. M. (2015). Situating and Constructing Diversity in semi-structured Interviews. *Global Qualitative Nursing Research*, 2(1), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2333393615597674>
- Mhlanga, D. (2023). Open AI in Education, the Responsible and Ethical Use of ChatGPT Towards Lifelong Learning. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4354422>
- Mindner, L., Schlippe, T., & Schaaff, K. (2023). Classification of Human- and AI-Generated Texts: Investigating Features for ChatGPT. *ArXiv (Cornell University)*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.2308.05341>
- O'Neill, R., & Russell, A. M. (2019). Grammarly: Help or hindrance? Academic learning advisors' perceptions of an online grammar checker. *Journal of Academic Language and Learning*, 13(1), A88-A107.
- Ouyang, F., & Jiao, P. (2021). Artificial Intelligence in Education: the Three Paradigms. *Computers and Education: Artificial Intelligence*, 2(1), 100020. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.caeai.2021.100020>
- Pascual, J. (2023, November 16). PH schools adopting AI; UP among first in Asia: group. *ABS-CBN News*; *ABS-CBN News*. <https://news.abs-cbn.com/business/11/16/23/ph-schools-adopting-ai-up-among-first-in-asia-group>
- Pavela, G. (1997). Applying the Power of Association on Campus: A Model Code of Academic Integrity. *Journal of College and University Law*, 24(1). https://www.heartland.edu/documents/idc/toomuch2_wrk.pdf
- Perkins, M. (2023). Academic integrity considerations of AI Large Language Models in the post-pandemic era: ChatGPT and beyond. *Journal of University Teaching and Learning Practice*, 20(2). <https://doi.org/10.53761/1.20.02.07>
- Pinkwart, N. (2016). Another 25 Years of AIED? Challenges and Opportunities for Intelligent Educational Technologies of the Future. *International Journal of Artificial Intelligence in Education*, 26(2), 771–783. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40593-016-0099-7>
- Popenici, S. A. D., & Kerr, S. (2017). Exploring the impact of artificial intelligence on teaching and learning in higher education. *Research and Practice in Technology Enhanced Learning*, 12(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41039-017-0062-8>
- Qadir, J. (2023). Engineering Education in the Era of ChatGPT: Promise and Pitfalls of Generative AI for Education. *2023 IEEE Global Engineering Education*

- Conference (EDUCON), 1–9.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/educon54358.2023.10125121>
- Qutoshi, S. B. (2018). Phenomenology: A philosophy and method of inquiry. *Journal of Education and Educational Development*, 5(1), 215–222.
<https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1180603>
- Rane, N., Choudhary, S., & Rane, J. (2023). Education 4.0 and 5.0: Integrating Artificial Intelligence (AI) for Personalized and Adaptive Learning. *Social Science Research Network*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4638365>
- Rasul, T., Nair, S., Kalendra, D., Robin, M., De Oliveira Santini, F., Ladeira, W. J., Sun, M., Day, I., Rather, R. A., & Heathcote, L. (2023). The role of ChatGPT in higher education: Benefits, challenges, and future research directions. *Journal of Applied Learning & Teaching*, 6(1). <https://doi.org/10.37074/jalt.2023.6.1.29>
- Russell, L., & Field-Springer, K. (2022). Phenomenology. *The International Encyclopedia of Health Communication*, 1–5.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119678816.iehc0601>
- Sabharwal, D., Kabha, R., & Srivastava, K. (2023). Artificial Intelligence (AI)-Powered Virtual Assistants and their Effect on Human Productivity and Laziness: Study on Students of Delhi-NCR (India) & Fujairah (UAE). *Journal of Content, Community & Communication*, 17(9), 162–174. <https://doi.org/10.31620/JCCC.06.23/12>
- Sarker, D., Eiaz-Ur-Rahman, A. F. M., Sakib, A. R., Terano, H. J. R., & Rahman, M. M. (2023). ChatGPT's Applications in Higher Education: Unmasking Opportunities and Challenges. *Journal of Education, Management and Development Studies*, 3(4), 37–47. <https://doi.org/10.52631/jemds.v3i4.250>
- Schwab, K. (2016, January 14). The Fourth Industrial Revolution: what it means, how to respond. *World Economic Forum*. <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2016/01/the-fourth-industrial-revolution-what-it-means-and-how-to-respond/>
- Sevnarayan, K., & Potter, M.-A. (2024). Generative Artificial Intelligence in distance education: Transformations, challenges, and impact on academic integrity and student voice. *Journal of Applied Learning and Teaching*, 7(1).
<https://doi.org/10.37074/jalt.2024.7.1.41>
- Siena, J. A., Bilbao, P., & Tuscano, F. J. (2019). On Leveraging ICT Tools in the Filipino K to 12 Classroom (D. Ocampo & K. L. M. Lucasan, Eds.; pp. 22–28). UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES CENTER FOR INTEGRATIVE AND DEVELOPMENT STUDIES. <https://cids.up.edu.ph/wp->

- content/uploads/2022/02/Key-Issues-in-Instruction-Teacher-Professional-Development-and-ICT-in-Basic-Education-2019.pdf
- Students: A Comprehensive Study. ERIC, ISSN-2835-3048, 31–42.
<https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED628620>
- Teel, Z. (Abbie), Wang, T., & Lund, B. (2023). ChatGPT conundrums: Probing plagiarism and parroting problems in higher education practices. *College & Research Libraries News*, 84(6). <https://doi.org/10.5860/crln.84.6.205>
- Tweissi, A., Al Etaiwi, W., & Al Eisawi, D. (2022). The Accuracy of AI-Based Automatic Proctoring in Online Exams. *Electronic Journal of E-Learning*, 20(4), 419–435.
<https://doi.org/10.34190/ejel.20.4.2600>
- Van Rijmenam, M. (2023, February 17). Privacy in the Age of AI: Risks, Challenges and Solutions. *The Digital Speaker | Strategic Futurist*.
<https://www.thedigitalspeaker.com/privacy-age-ai-risks-challenges-solutions/>
- Wogu, I. A. P., Misra, S., Olu-Owolabi, E. F., Assibong, P. A., Udoh, O. D., Ogiri, S. O., & Damasevicius, R. (2018). Artificial Intelligence, Artificial Teachers and the Fate of Learners in the 21st Century Education Sector: Implications for Theory and Practice. *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics*, 119(16), 2245–2259.
- Yeralan, S., & Lee, L. A. (2023). Generative AI: Challenges to higher education. *Sustainable Engineering and Innovation*, 5(2), 107–116.
<https://doi.org/10.37868/sei.v5i2.id196>
- Zhai, X., Chu, X., Chai, C. S., Jong, M. S. Y., Istenic, A., Spector, M., Liu, J.-B., Yuan, J., & Li, Y. (2021). A Review of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Education from 2010 to 2020. *Complexity*, 2021(8812542), 1–18.
<https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/8812542>